

**EVALUATION OF PROXIMITY AND MORPHOLOGY OF NASOPALATINE
CANAL POSITION RELATIVE TO THE MAXILLARY CENTRAL INCISOR
AMONG GENDER USING CONE BEAM COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY- AN
ANALYTICAL STUDY**

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Abstract: Implant placement immediately after tooth extraction was introduced in the late 1980s to reduce treatment time and help preserve alveolar bone. However, when immediate implant placement is warranted at the maxillary central incisor positions, the presence of the nasopalatine canal (NPC) may limit the amount of available bone for primary implant stability. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) has been used extensively in dentistry because of its ability to produce adequately accurate two- and three-dimensional images

Aim and Objectives: Evaluation of proximity and morphology of nasopalatine canal position relative to the maxillary central incisor among gender using cone beam computed tomography.

Materials and Methods: A total of 174 CBCT Scans were considered for the study each group consisted of 87 male and 87 female patients scan. It was analytical type of study.

Results: Men demonstrate slightly greater Nasopalatine canal to maxillary central incisor root distance than women(at both the levels i.e at apex of MCIR to NPC canal and Mid-root of MCIR to NPC canal).

There were considerable Variation in morphology of NPC, and the distance of NPC from MCIR even within subjects of the same race.

Keywords: Maxillary central incisor, CBCT ,morphological variations, nasopalatine canal.

Introduction

Since the discovery of the X-rays different radiographic techniques have been used in dental radiography and due to this, dental imaging has done tremendous progress in various fields of dentistry. The 2-D Conventional radiographs provide excellent images for most dental radiographic needs. . However, the reliability of measurements obtained by this method is low due to distortion and magnification inherent in the technique.¹ Due to this new technologic innovation in image acquisition processes and the development of networked computing systems for image retrieval and transmission is developed².

One of the most commonly cited positive features of digital radiography is the radiation dose reduction up to 80%, when compared with conventional plain film radiography. However, in case of diagnostic dilemma and treatment planning of special cases, advanced 3-D imaging

modalities, revealing additional information is desirable. Various techniques have evolved in the recent past that has revolutionized the diagnosis and treatment planning in dentistry³

However, cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) has recently been proposed as a valuable three dimensional imaging technique in dentistry. Compared to spiral tomography, CBCT has the advantage of high resolution and elimination of superimposition. In addition, compared to computed tomography (CT), CBCT has many benefits, including lower radiation dose, shorter imaging time and high resolution (less than a millimeter). CBCT technology has facilitated the precise three-dimensional evaluation of bone quantity and it can produce views and volumetric reconstructions of craniofacial structures which aids in accurate treatment planning in Implant placement.

Nowadays patient wants tooth replacement in minimal time period which has led to the development of immediate implant placement in which anatomic conditions like the presence of nerves and vessels and bone thickness are vital factors which can be very well understood through CBCT imaging.³

Maxillary anterior region is the most common region prone to trauma and tooth loss; therefore, it often requires surgical interventions such as implant placement.⁴ During implant placement in the anterior region of the maxilla, attention should be paid to the atrophy of the alveolar bone following the loss of incisors and also to the morphology and position of the nasopalatine canal.⁵ Any contact between the implant and the nasopalatine nerve may result in the failure of implant osseointegration or in neurological dysfunction

The Nasopalatine canal is an important anatomic structure present in the midline of the anterior maxilla that connects the palate to the floor of the nasal cavity⁶. It is also known as the incisive canal or anterior palatine canal.

The oral opening of the canal in the oral cavity is called the incisive foramen (IF) and is located in the middle line of the anterior upper jaw under the incisive papilla. The NPC ends in the nasal cavity with two divided openings at each side of the nasal septum and is known as the Stensen's foramina (SF).⁷

Inside the bone, the NPC divides in the cranial course into two tubes that run separately to the nasal aperture, termed nasal foramina. The NPC contains fibrillary connective and adipose tissues, minor salivary glands and the nasopalatine nerve and artery. During its osseous passage, the artery maintains anastomoses with the major palatine artery⁸.

Occasionally, two additional small channels are found in the incisive bone medial to the NPC (canals of Scarpa). These channels carry further nerve filaments of the nasopalatine nerve, terminating in the incisive foramen as Scarpa's foramina. In the oral cavity, the left supplementary channel opens anteriorly and the right posteriorly to the oral opening of the NPC.⁹

The NPC should not be confused with the paired nasopalatine or incisive duct. This duct develops prenatally in the 6th to 12th fetal weeks from epithelia within the NPC and forms a temporary connection between the nasal and oral cavities during the 13th and 14th fetal weeks.¹⁰⁻¹¹

Several morphological alterations in the incisive canal shape have been described; **Mardinger et al.** Classified incisive canal shape as cylindrical, funnel like, banana like, and hour-glass like. Size, shape, position, and number of foramina vary in different individuals. Presence of wider foramina and thin alveolar bone anterior to the canal may make an implant placement almost impossible in this area.¹² **Bornstein et al.** evaluated the dimensions and characteristics of nasopalatine canal (NPC) via CBCT images as a) single duct; (b) two parallel ducts; and c) variations of Y-type ducts with one oral/palatal opening and two or more nasal openings¹³.

So the knowledge of precise anatomical descriptions, dimensions, and the location of the NPC is crucial in the fields of dentistry and oral and maxillofacial surgery, e.g. for local anesthesia of the anterior maxilla, and the planning of surgical procedures concerning this region, such as dental implant placement or apical root resection. Surgery in the anterior maxilla can give rise to contact of surgical instruments and implants with the structures running through or close to the NPC¹³. This situation may cause surgical problems and lead to sensory dysfunction or poor osseointegration of implants.¹⁴

Previous studies investigated the morphology of the canal using CT or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and CBCT assessments are rare with small sample sizes. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) has ability to produce adequately accurate two- and three-dimensional images.¹⁵ Furthermore, the use of a cone-shaped X-ray beam and a more restricted field of view in the axial dimension produces a relatively low effective radiation dose compared with conventional medical computed tomography. Moreover, linear measurements made from CBCT images are not significantly different from the actual direct measurements of anatomic structures in the dentomaxillofacial area.¹⁵

According to **Jacobs et al**,¹⁶ surgical interventions in NPC area have been increased significantly. Awareness about the anatomical variations of the NPC is fundamental for avoiding neurovascular bundles damage. To avoid injury to the nerve and vessel within the canal and its subsequent complications such as hemorrhage and sensory dysfunction, dental implants must be placed at an adequate distance from NPC.¹⁷⁻¹⁸

The purpose of this study was to measure the relative proximity of the NPC to the maxillary central incisor root (MCIR) using CBCT images and to evaluate the morphology, of NPC in CBCT images.

Aim of the study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the relative proximity and morphology of Nasopalatine canal position to the maxillary central incisor between males and females using Cone Beam Computed Tomography

Objectives of the study

- 1) To assess and measure the relative proximity of nasopalatine canal to the roots of maxillary central incisor in males and females by using cone beam computed tomography.
- 2) To study the morphologic characteristics of the nasopalatine canal by using cone beam computed tomography in males and females.
- 3) To compare the relative proximity of nasopalatine canal to the roots of maxillary central incisor and morphologic characteristics of the nasopalatine canal in males and females by using cone beam computed tomography.

Materials and Methods

The present analytical study was conducted in the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology which was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee. The data was obtained from scanned images of CBCT taken for various purposes and it was evaluated.

Inclusion criteria:

- 1) Cone beam computed image of anterior palate taken for various diagnostic purposes was retrieved from the period February 2018 to June 2020 and evaluated.
- 2) Age group 21 years and above.
- 3) Presence of both maxillary central incisors.

Exclusion criteria:

- 1) Anterior edentulous patients.
- 2) Patients suffering from severe periodontitis
- 4) Impacted tooth/teeth in maxillary central incisors region.
- 5) Presence of pathology associated with maxillary central incisor

Study design: Observational Analytical study.

Sample size:

Patients Scans were categorized into 2 groups

Group A- 87 Males

Group B- 87 Females

Total 174 scans of CBCT were considered for evaluation.

Sampling Technique: Stratified random sampling technique.

The source of data for the study was all scanned images of anterior maxillary CBCT. Out of which 87 male and 87 female scans were selected from this sampling frame using random number table.

Using the distance measurement tool in the CBCT software the distance between

- 1) Nasopalatine canal-to-Maxillary Central incisor root at the middle of the root length (midroot level) and
- 2) Nasopalatine canal to the apex level of both maxillary central incisor was measured.
- 3) Also the morphologic variation of male and female nasopalatine canals were assessed based on **Bornstein et al**⁴³ classification as follows:

- 1) Type A canal (Single canal)

- 2) Type B canal (2 parallel canals)
- 3) Type C canal (Y shaped canal)

Fig 1: Distance from Nasopalatine canal to mid-root of maxillary central incisor

Fig 2: Distance from Nasopalatine canal to Apex of maxillary central incisor root

FIG 3 Type A single canal

FIG 4 and 5: Type B and C canal

Table 2: Assessment of mid-root to nasopalatine canal distance on left side and right side by gender

Mid-root to nasopalatine canal distance (in mm)	Male	Male	Female	Female
	Left side	Right side	Left side	Right side
Mean	2.24	2.24	2.19	2.14
SD ±	0.62	0.80	0.50	0.63
Minimum	1.31	1.20	1.25	1.09
Maximum	3.93	5.60	3.61	4.00

Table 3:

Comparison of mid-root to nasopalatine canal distance in male versus female on each side.

Mid-root to nasopalatine canal distance (in mm)	Male Left side	Female Left side	Male Right side	Female Right side
Mean	2.24	2.19	2.24	2.14
SD±	0.62	0.50	0.80	0.63
P value (by unpaired t-test)	P= 0.5540, NS		P= 0.3671, NS	

Table 2 and 3 illustrate descriptive statistics, t value, p value, of mid –root to nasopalatine distance in males and females. This table showed the comparison of mid root to nasopalatine distance among males and females, with respect to maxillary central incisor tooth, the dimension was 2.24 ± 0.62 mm on left side and 2.19 ± 0.80 mm on right side in males whereas 2.19 ± 0.50 mm on left side and 2.14 ± 0.63 mm in females with p value of 0.5540 and 0.3671 respectively which was found to be statistically not significant.

Table 4: Assessment of apical area to nasopalatine canal distance on left side and right side by gender

Apical area to nasopalatine canal distance (in mm)	Male Left side	Male Right side	Female Left side	Female Right side
Mean	2.74	2.69	2.69	2.60
SD±	0.64	0.75	0.62	0.66
Minimum	1.40	1.37	0.093	1.17
Maximum	4.57	4.60	4.40	4.60

Table 5: Comparison of apical area to nasopalatine canal distance in male versus female on each side

Apical area to nasopalatine canal distance (in mm)	Male	Female	Male	Female
	Left side	Left side	Right side	Right side
Mean	2.74	2.69	2.69	2.60
SD±	0.64	0.62	0.75	0.66
P value (by unpaired t-test)	P= 0.5745, NS		P= 0.3902, NS	

Table 4, 5 illustrate descriptive statistics, t value, p value, of apical to nasopalatine distance between males and females. It showed the comparison of apical to nasopalatine distance among males and females, with respect to maxillary central incisor tooth, the dimension was 2.74 ± 0.64 mm on left side and 2.69 ± 0.75 mm on right side in males whereas it was 2.69 ± 0.62 mm on left side and 2.60 ± 0.66 mm on right side in females. On comparison the p value of 0.5745 and 0.3902 on left and right side respectively which was found to be statistically not significant.

Table 6: Morphology variation in males and females

Type	Male		Female		p value (by Z test)
(n=87)	%		(n= 87)		%
A	84	96.55	79	90.80	0.1193, NS
B	1	1.15	2	2.30	0.5603, NS
C	2	2.30	2	2.30	1.000, NS

Table 6 illustrate the Types of canal prevalent in males and females. The p value was calculated by Z test.

In present study, 96.55% males and 90.80% females showed Type A canal while Type B canal was seen in 1.15% males and 2.30% females and Type C canal was seen in 2.30% each in males and females. On comparison the p value was found to be statically not significant.

Discussion

Dental implants have proven to be a predictable modality for replacing missing teeth. Nowadays most of the dental patients are opting for dental implants as a means of tooth replacement instead of fixed prosthesis. Also young patients whose teeth are missing due to trauma insist for immediate implant placement to reduce waiting time for aesthetic purpose. More than 30 years of evidence on the clinical use of endosseous implants has revealed satisfactory long-term results.¹⁹⁻²⁰

The clinician proceeds with the immediate implants as there is possibility of continued alveolar bone resorption following tooth extraction . During the period of development, the concepts of implant and protocol for implant have undergone tremendous changes. According to the **Brånemark (1983)** protocol of 1983, a stress-free healing period is one of the most emphasized requirements for predictable implant integration. Initially implant placement involved two-stage surgery which provided reproducible and reliable results with a submerged healing period of 4 to 6 months.²¹

Though associated with highly successful outcomes this traditional protocol implies a long period of treatment, multiple surgeries, as well as the discomfort and embarrassment of wearing removable prostheses during transition. As a consequence of patient's demand for fewer surgical interventions and shorter healing periods prior to loading, changes in clinical procedures were proposed, such as the insertion of implants into fresh extraction sites (immediate placement) and the installation of the prosthesis immediately after implantation.²²⁻²³

Traditionally, two-dimensional methods like intra-oral radiography and panoramic imaging have been used in the literature for diagnostic imaging of the anterior maxilla. However, the introduction of cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) has created new diagnostic possibilities in dentistry. CBCT scans have made it possible to analyse 3D anatomical variations of the Nasopalatine Canal ²⁴⁻²⁵ and to determine the degree of Buccal Bone Plate/Palatal bone plate resorption in the anterior maxillary region after tooth loss ²⁶. Keeping in mind that the Nasopalatine canal (NPC) may occupy up to 58 % of the Labial Bone Plate ²⁷, a precise 3-dimensional (3D) anatomic description of the NPC to enable safe and accurate surgical planning and placement of dental implants is necessary. ²⁸

This analytical cross sectional study was carried out to evaluate the relative proximity and morphology of Nasopalatine canal position to the maxillary central incisor between males and females using Cone Beam Computed Tomography. Total 174 subjects CBCT scans were evaluated among them 87 scans were of males and 87 scans of females.

Using distance measurement tool in Xelis software we measured the distance between NPC and Maxillary central incisor (MCIR) root at apex and mid root level of male and female. Factors such as Age group ≥ 21 years and presence of both maxillary central incisors were considered as inclusion criteria for the study. Similarly some factors considered as exclusion criteria for the study are, anterior edentulous patients, patients suffering from severe periodontitis, Impacted tooth/teeth in maxillary central incisors region, presence of pathology associated with maxillary central incisor. All these factors were in accordance with the study conducted by **Pakawat Chatriyanuyoke et al (2012)**.²⁹

As per the present study the demographic data of 174 CBCT scans included 22 scans of males and 27 scans of females in the age group of 21-30 years, 45 males and 38 females in the age group of 31-40 years and 20 males and 22 females in the age group 41-50 years which showed that there are more number of subject in the middle age group (i.e.31-40 years).

In the present study the distance from **Mid-root** Maxillary central incisors to NPC in male on left side was **$2.24 \pm 0.62\text{mm}$** and **$2.24 \pm 0.80\text{mm}$** on right side. While the distance from **Mid-root** of Maxillary central incisors to NPC in female on left and right side was **$2.19 \pm 0.50\text{mm}$** and **$2.14 \pm 0.63\text{mm}$** respectively.

On comparing the distances from mid-root of Maxillary central incisors to NPC between male and females the **p value was 0.5540** on left side and **0.3671** on right side, which was statistically not significant. The present study finding were in contrast to **Pakawat Chatriyanuoke et al(2012)**²⁵ where stastically significant results with **p value 0.2 and 0.4** on right and left side of male and female was documented. Furthermore, close approximation between the NPC-to-MCIR distances was also observed by **Pakawat Chatriyanuoke et al (2012)**²⁵ on multiple occasions. This may be because **Pakawat Chatriyanuoke et al (2012)**²⁵ included more number of younger age group subjects in the study. While in our study there was more number of subjects in the age between 31-40 years. This may be due to different geographic area, ethnicity and race.

Also the distance from Nasopalatine canal (NPC) to **Apex** of Maxillary central incisor in male was **$2.74 \pm 0.62\text{mm}$** on left side and **$2.69 \pm 0.75\text{mm}$** on right side.

In female the distance from **Apex** of Maxillary central incisor to NPC on left and right side was **$2.69 \pm 0.62\text{mm}$** and **$2.60 \pm 0.66\text{mm}$** respectively. The finding were in accordance with the

study conducted by **Pakawat Chatriyanuyoke et al (2012)**²⁰ where the distance from Nasopalatine canal (NPC) to **Apex** of Maxillary central in males was **5.51±1.67mm** on right side and **5.42±1.51mm** on left side. In female the distance from **Apex** of Maxillary central incisor to NPC was **4.98±1.42mm** on right side and **4.97±1.29mm** on left side where male demonstrate slightly greater distance from apex to MCIR than female.

According to the literature, the shape of the adult male and female face differs significantly in both qualitative and quantitative terms: the difference covers both hard and soft tissue components.³⁰⁻³¹ Present study predicted that male teeth would occupy different shape than female teeth, indicating a sexual dimorphism in dental arch type.

But on comparing the distances from Apex of Maxillary central incisor root to NPC in males and females p value was **0.5745** on left side and **0.3902** on right side which was not stastically significant. Present study findings were in accordance with the study conducted by **Pakawat Chatriyanuyoke et al (2012)**²⁹ in which the p value was **0.08** on left side and **0.06** on right side in males and females.

Clinically implant engagement initiates with socket wall at mid-root area in palatal aspect while it should extend 4mm beyond the apex of extraction socket in apical aspect. Thus more amount of palatal bone is required for implant engagement in the apical direction³². In present study male demonstrated slightly greater distance from apex of MCIR to NPC than female. As a result, the NPC-MCIR approximation must be carefully assessed during treatment planning for immediate implant placement. Tapered implants, which need less bone for implant engagement apically and have been shown to achieve improved primary stability, may be advantageous for immediate implant placement in the maxillary central incisor location in both males and females.³³

In the present study amongst 87 male and 87 female CBCT scans **Type A** canal was present in 84 (96.55%) males and 79(90.80%) in females, **Type B** canal was present in 1(1.15%) male and 2 (2.30%) females and **Type C** was present in 2(2.30%) males and 2 females. These results were in accordance with study conducted by **Etoz et al(2014)**³⁴ where morphological assessments of Nasopalatine canal showed increased number of individual **Type A** single canals (96.1 %) compared to **Type B** double canals (3.9 %) Similarly the study conducted by **Bornstein et al (2011)**¹⁹ identified maximum number of **Type A canal** (45 cases) compared to **Type B canal** (15 cases) and **Type C canal** (40 cases).

Study conducted by **Ahmet Ercan Sekerci et al (2014)**³⁵ also demonstrated more number of **Type A canal** in 226 cases ,**Type B canal** were detected in 36 cases and **Type C canal** were seen in 106 cases.

Similar findings with regard to the frequency of a single-canal configuration were reported in a recent study on 56 human cadavers, where microscopic computed tomography of the anterior maxilla was performed by **Song et al. 2009**³⁶.

The present study findings are in contradiction with those of **Yasir et al. (2016)**³⁰ and **Bahsi et al. (2019)**⁴⁰, who found that **Type C canals** were more common than **Type A canals** and **Type B canals**. This may be due to the larger sample size of 326 subjects, as well as the inclusion of younger subjects (>18 years old) and people of different ethnicities and geographical backgrounds, such as those from Iran and Turkey.

Literature demonstrated that the NPC displays many morphological as well as dimensional variations. Present study and similar other studies may be of clinical importance in administering local anesthesia, maxillary surgery, and implant surgery in premaxillary area. Improved identification of anatomical structures may increase surgical success and prevent postoperative complications like neurovascular damage. For this reason, careful preoperative planning using low-dose 3D imaging with CBCT is recommended.³⁷

Conclusion

This study was conducted to measure the relative proximity of the NPC to the apex of maxillary central incisor root (MCIR) and from NPC to Mid root area of MCIR using CBCT images and to evaluate the morphology of NPC in maxillary anterior region with the help of CBCT images.

It was analytical observational study. The source of data for the study was the Cone Beam Computed Tomography scans of the patients who reported to the department of oral Medicine and Radiology. A stratified random sample of 87 male and 87 female Cone beam Computed tomography (Sironaorthophos SL) scans were selected from this sampling frame using random number table. Using the distance measurement tool in the CBCT Xelis software the distance between Nasopalatine canal-to-Maxillary Central incisor root at the midroot level and from NPC to the apex level of both maxillary central incisor were measured. Also the morphologic variation of male and female nasopalatine canals based on **Bornstein et al** classification was assessed respectively.

The following conclusion were drawn:

Men demonstrate slightly greater Nasopalatine canal to maxillary central incisor root distance than women (at both the levels i.e at apex of MCIR to NPC canal and Mid-root of MCIR to

NPC canal) though it was not statistically significant in present study .It may be because of the relatively larger craniocaudal dimension of the face in the males as compared to the females.

Presence of considerable Variation in morphology of NPC, and the distance of NPC from MCIR even within subjects of the same race indicates the influence of age and gender and ethnicity.

This study contributes to the knowledge of anatomical morphology of the NPC and dimensions that can serve as a helpful reference. Increased knowledge of this anatomic structure and its diversity leads to enhanced surgical procedures and reduced complications. When planning dental implants, carrying out radiographic examinations, alongside clinical examinations, has become necessary to reduce the risk of implant surgery failure and hurdles. The CBCT imaging is a valuable tool to determine the anatomic structures before any surgery, including implant surgery.

A through anatomical knowledge of NPC and its proximity with MCIR can be very helpful for selection of Implant to avoid trauma and neurovascular damage to Nasopalatine canal.

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